

PREPARING FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS FOR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY

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Annotation. This article contains suggestions and recommendations on how to prepare future biology teachers for innovative activities, to improve the skills of teachers.

Keywords: biology, independent work, creativity, professional competence.

Information is a collection of messages about objects, events, processes. The development of modern education is giving rise to a new direction, innovative activity. Innovative activity is explained by the following main functions:

- conscious analysis of professional activity;
- critical approach to norms;
- ready for professional news;
- a creative approach to the world.

Realizing one's potential, incorporating one's lifestyle and aspirations into one's professional life is reflected in a teacher's innovative activity. Innovative activity includes the analysis and evaluation of innovation, the formation of goals and concepts of future actions, the implementation of this plan, the evaluation of effectiveness.

The effectiveness of innovative activities is determined by the personality of the teacher. One of the main ways to improve the educational process is to humanize the educational process and democratize it as an innovative process.

The following rules should be followed in humanizing the lesson:

- cooperation;
- student care;
- respect;
- to be forgiving
- creating an environment for self-development;
- creating a psychologically healthy environment;
- creative environment;
- to be friendly;
- student needs, interests, personal qualities, talents. [1]

To increase the effectiveness of innovative activities, the teacher must have the following skills:

- cognitive management;

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- technological;
- speech;
- communicativeness;
- age of the student, suitability for internal capacity.

Innovation, expressing the pedagogical process, applies not only to its didactic structure, but also to the socially significant outcomes and mental image of the teacher. Innovation means openness, recognition of the opinion of others [2].

The innovative activity of the teacher is based on the dynamics of conflict and mutual enrichment of different points of view. The effectiveness of a teacher's innovation depends on a number of factors. It includes the teacher's impartiality in dealing with dissent, the willingness of the teacher to accept the recognition of a rational situation in different situations. As a result, the teacher has a wide range of topics (motives) that support their knowledge and research.

Themes of self-activation, creativity, self-knowledge and creativity are important in the work of a teacher. This allows the teacher to be more creative [3].

An important condition for innovation is to create a new state of communication.

A new state of communication is the ability of a teacher to create his own position of independence, a new attitude to the world, to pedagogical science, to himself. In such cases, the teacher's way of thinking, mental culture changes, emotional feelings develop.

Motivates students to be motivated, active, and responsible, making them the driving force behind the learning process. In turn, it guarantees quality and efficiency in education.

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